

Strategies for the valorization of shrimp by-products through the application of PULSED ELECTRIC FIELDS (PEF) AND ACCELERATED SOLVENT EXTRACTION (ASE) treatments

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Introduction

An important category of by-products from seafood processing includes crustacean ones. Approximately 6-8 million tons of crustacean waste is produced worldwide every year (FAO, 2014). Shrimp and prawns are one of the most important internationally traded seafood products, and one of the few that can be considered a “commodity”, with a value of US\$10 billion (or 16% of world fishery exports) (Gillett, 2008). Shrimp by-products represent important natural sources of carotenoid, among which astaxanthin (ASX) is the major one. Recently, pulsed electric field (PEF) treatment may be a promising method for the isolation and extraction of several components from seafood by-products such as calcium, chondroitin sulphate, collagen, chitosan, and protein (Bruno et al., 2019). Accelerated solvent extraction (ASE) is considered a green technique to recover bioactive and nutritional compounds in plants and food matrices (Sun et al., 2012). The main objective of the present study was to apply PEF and ASE using two organic solvents (dimethyl sulfoxide, DMSO and ethanol, EtOH) to recovery ASX from shrimp by-products and evaluate the effects of these technologies used independently or in combination on the ASX content and antioxidant activities of the extracts.

Materials and methods

In this study, fresh samples of red shrimp (*Aristeus antennatus*) and camarote shrimp (*Melicerus kerathurus*) were obtained from a local market in Valencia, Spain. Dimethyl sulfoxide (100% DMSO) or ethanol absolute (EtOH) were used as organic solvents. The combined and independent effects of the emerging technologies PEF and ASE using different solvents (EtOH and DMSO) on the extraction of astaxanthin were evaluated for each shrimp species (*M. kerathurus* and *A. antennatus*). ASE (50 °C, 15 min, 103.4 bar) and PEF (3 kV/cm, 100 kJ/kg, 74 pulses) were used as extraction technologies. The antioxidant capacity of the extracts was evaluated by Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (TEAC) and oxygen radical absorbance capacity (ORAC) assays. Experimental data were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the significant differences among samples. Tukey HSD (Honestly Significant Difference) multiple range test, at a significance level of $p < 0.05$ was applied.

Results

Preliminary results showed that ASE and PEF increased the astaxanthin content in the extracts for both shrimp species and solvent used, and the higher recovery was obtained using their combination (Fig 1).

Figure 1: Astaxanthin content in *M. kerathurus* (a) and *A. antennatus* (b) by-products. Different letters above the bars indicate statistically significant differences between treatment averages ($P < 0.05$).

Both technologies seem to be an effective tool to recover astaxanthin and antioxidant extracts from shrimp by-products, however these promising results should be confirmed by extending the study to other valuable compounds from crustacean by-products.

References

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